

Invisible vectors, visible impact: The role of eriophyoid mites in emaravirus disease dynamics

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Abstract

Emaraviruses are segmented, negative-sense RNA viruses that are transmitted by eriophyoid mites. Advances in virus detection and discovery have significantly improved our understanding of these viruses, yet several challenges persist. This review emphasizes the significant gaps in our knowledge of virus replication, transmission dynamics, and plant-virus-vector interactions and highlights the role of mite vectors in the epidemiology and control of emaraviruses. By bridging the knowledge gaps with advanced genomic tools such as high throughput sequencing and bioinformatics and targeted acarological research we will achieve sustainable control strategies and reduce the impact of emaravirus-caused diseases.

Keywords: transmission, replication, epidemiology, control

Introduction

Emaraviruses are found everywhere in the world where the conditions are conducive for their hosts and vectors. Although diseases caused by emaraviruses were documented as early as the early 20th century (Condit & Horne, 1933; Mitra, 1924), it was not until the advent of high-throughput sequencing (HTS) at the turn of the 21st century that

33 our understanding of these viruses and their impact on agriculture advanced
34 significantly (Mielke-Ehret & Mühlbach, 2012). The seminal moment occurred with the
35 publication of the sequence of European mountain ash ringspot-associated emaravirus
36 (EMARaV) initially believed to represent the entire genome of the virus (Mielke &
37 Muehlbach, 2007). Since then, the genus has expanded to include over 35 recognized
38 or putative members (Digiario et al., 2024, Table 1) with a growing body of literature on
39 their characterization, epidemiology, and control (Druciarek et al., 2024a; Kubota et al.,
40 2020a; Novick, 2017; Patil et al., 2021; Shimomoto et al., 2022).

41 Emaraviruses are still under-recognized due to several factors. First, the fragile
42 nature of emaravirus particles makes them difficult to isolate. In addition, many
43 emaravirus hosts are woody plants, which present unique challenges for virological
44 research due to the abundance of secondary metabolites that interfere with molecular
45 biology techniques (Tzanetakis et al., 2005). Additionally, their multisegmented
46 genomes complicate their study, as determining the exact number of segments that
47 comprise the complete emaravirus genome has been and is still challenging.
48 Furthermore, their natural arthropod vectors are microscopic and difficult to handle.
49 Together, these factors complicate the study of emaraviruses.

50 A critical aspect of understanding the epidemiology of any virus is the
51 identification and characterization of its vectors. In the case of emaraviruses, their
52 vectors are eriophyoid mites (Acari: Eriophyoidea), the smallest arthropods of
53 agricultural importance. These mites, typically measuring $\sim 200 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$, are invisible to
54 the naked eye and require specialized training in acarology for proper study, with
55 manipulation generally performed under a stereoscope. Furthermore, many eriophyoid
56 mites tend to occupy obscure parts of the plant, making it even more challenging to
57 study their behavior and interactions with emaraviruses (Stenger et al., 2016).

58 The known incidence of diseases caused by emaraviruses has been rising, with
59 several species causing severe disease, even plant death (Jones et al., 2004; Laney et
60 al., 2011). This growing threat has prompted research groups to focus on the vector-
61 virus pathosystems, aiming to enhance our understanding of these diseases and

62 develop effective, durable control measures. Initial efforts focused on elucidating the
63 nature of the causal agents, identifying their vectors (Allington et al., 1968; Jones et al.,
64 1984; Seifers et al., 1997), and developing diagnostic assays (Dobhal et al., 2016;
65 Elbeaino et al., 2013; Kubota et al., 2021a; Olmedo-Velarde et al., 2023). As these
66 efforts continue, there is a parallel push to better understand the biology and diversity
67 of emaraviruses and develop effective and sustainable control measures to mitigate
68 their impact (e.g., Gupta et al., 2018; Jones et al., 2023; Minguely et al., 2021; Tatineni
69 et al., 2014; Young et al., 2022).

70 Given the advances in our understanding of emaraviruses and their vectors over
71 the past decade, revisiting this topic is essential. The review is structured to guide the
72 reader through the complexities of emaravirus epidemiology and control. We will
73 provide an overview of the molecular characteristics and biology of emaraviruses and
74 examine the mite vectors, discussing their role in virus transmission. We will then
75 explore the epidemiology of emaravirus-caused diseases, analyzing patterns of spread,
76 environmental factors, and the impact of agricultural practices on disease dynamics.
77 This review will conclude with a discussion of current and emerging strategies for
78 controlling disease outbreaks, emphasizing integrated pest management approaches
79 and the potential for future innovations in disease control. Throughout, we will highlight
80 existing knowledge gaps and suggest potential directions for future research that could
81 enhance our ability to manage the challenges posed by emaravirus-caused diseases.

82

83 **Emaraviruses, the epitome of genome plasticity**

84 Building on the recent, comprehensive review of emaraviruses in the ICTV report on the
85 family *Fimoviridae* (Digiario et al., 2024), as well as insights from other reviews (de Lillo
86 et al., 2021; Rehanek et al., 2022), we aim to provide an accessible overview of the
87 foundational knowledge to help novice readers engage with this article.

88 Emaraviruses (family *Fimoviridae*, order *Elliovirales*) are segmented, largely
89 monocistronic, negative-sense RNA viruses that are encapsulated in pleomorphic,
90 enveloped particles of ~100 nm in diameter. Double-membrane-bound bodies (DMBs)

91 have been observed in infected cells in proximity to the endoplasmic reticulum and
92 Golgi apparatus of mesophyll cells of emaravirus-infected jujube, kiwifruit, pigeonpea,
93 rose, ash and fig (Gaskin et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2002; Martelli et al., 1993; Yang et
94 al., 2019; Zheng et al., 2017) and are thought to facilitate viral replication (Elbeaino et
95 al., 2009a; Gaskin et al., 2021; Gergerich & Kim, 1983; Yang et al., 2024). Similar
96 bodies or vesicles were observed in other RNA virus-infected cells. They are formed
97 through the remodeling of host cellular membranes and enhance virus replication
98 efficiency by providing a scaffold for the assembly of replication machinery and protect
99 viral components from degradation by host cellular mechanisms (Belov et al., 2012;
100 Schaad et al., 1997).

101 Emaravirus replication at-large is understudied, but all evidence (primarily
102 electron micrographs) points to a strategy similar to that of orthospoviruses—
103 cytoplasmic replication (Kikkert et al., 1999). The termini of the genomic segments are
104 complementary, facilitating circular or panhandle-like structures of segments allowing
105 for efficient template recognition and transcription as well as protection from
106 exonucleases. Translation is accommodated by cap snatching of host mRNAs as the
107 genomic RNAs are not capped whereas the mRNAs are (Laney et al., 2011; Walia &
108 Falk, 2012).

109 The emaravirus genome structure is particularly notable for its plasticity,
110 adapting across various species and even within a single viral population. There are
111 emaraviruses with as few as four genomic segments (Peracchio et al., 2020), whereas
112 others have as many as ten (Kubota et al., 2020a). Even within the same species, the
113 number of genomic segments can fluctuate (Stewart, 2016), with some encoding
114 proteins that appear to be paralogs, given that their amino acid sequences are more
115 similar to each other, than any other protein found in the protein databases.

116 All members of the group encode four core proteins that are involved in
117 replication, encapsidation/genome protection, and movement. RNA1 encodes for the
118 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase, which has all the *Bunyaviricetes* polymerase motifs
119 (Laney et al., 2011). RNA2 encodes for the viral precursor glycoprotein, predicted to be

120 cleaved into two mature peptides with several glycosylation sites and transmembrane
121 domains, presumably allowing them to embed into the membrane particles (Laney et
122 al., 2011). RNA3 encodes for the viral nucleoprotein, which forms a tetramer
123 accommodating virus RNA binding (Izhaki-Tavor et al., 2023). RNA4 concludes the core
124 segments that, in the case of rose rosette emaravirus (RRV), allow for independent
125 virus replication (Verchot et al., 2020) and encodes a 30K-type movement protein
126 (Ishikawa et al., 2013; Yu et al., 2013). Both RNAs 3 and 4 have occasionally
127 undergone duplication within the individual genomes. This duplication may increase
128 functional versatility, though its evolutionary benefits are still under study (Kubota et
129 al., 2020a; Tatineni et al., 2014; Yang et al., 2019).

130 The role of the proteins in the additional emaravirus RNAs is not well studied,
131 and it is not uncommon that the protein name/numbering of one virus does not
132 represent the ortholog in another. There is evidence that in emaraviruses with more
133 than four segments, some proteins may be involved in RNA silencing (Gupta et al.,
134 2018, 2019; Hamo et al., 2024; Ren et al., 2024), whereas structural simulations in
135 others point to protease function (Rehanek et al., 2022), though this is yet to be
136 experimentally validated. Understanding the full extent of emaravirus genome functions
137 and plasticity and its impact on viral adaptability could reveal new insights into
138 emaravirus-vector-host interactions and inform future control strategies.

139

140 **Eriophyoid mites, an uncharted territory**

141 A thorough understanding of vectors is essential for developing effective control
142 strategies for managing vector-borne diseases. Interactions between viruses, their
143 hosts, and vectors (including the host/vector microbiome) play a pivotal role in shaping
144 the evolution of all parties involved. As the incidence of emaraviruses continues to rise
145 globally, innovative research efforts that integrate ecological, biological, and
146 environmental perspectives will be critical in mitigating their impact. However, progress
147 is significantly hindered in the case of eriophyoid mites, primarily due to the lack of
148 genetic and genomic resources for this group. The classification of the superfamily

149 Eriophyoidea, which encompasses all known eriophyoid species, has traditionally relied
150 on morphological traits, which, due to the limited number of reliable diagnostic
151 characters, led to taxonomic inaccuracies (Lindquist & Amrine, 1996; Lindquist &
152 Oldfield, 1996). Moreover, the widely accepted classification system for eriophyoids
153 relies on unpolarized characters, which have been repeatedly used across various
154 taxonomic levels. This reliance hinders the accurate determination of evolutionary
155 relationships, including whether a given character is ancestral or a more recent
156 adaptation (Amrine et al., 2003). In addition, certain morphological traits used to
157 determine phylogenetic positions within Eriophyoidea have been identified as
158 homoplastic. These traits have evolved independently in unrelated lineages due to
159 convergent evolution, rather than being inherited from a common ancestor (Li et al.,
160 2014), affecting morphology-based taxonomic classifications. Cryptic species further
161 complicate identification because genetically distinct mites cannot be separated
162 morphologically (Matsuda et al., 2013; Skoracka et al., 2015; Yin et al., 2022).
163 Conversely, some species, including confirmed vectors, exhibit complex life cycles
164 known as deuteroecy, featuring two distinct female forms: protogyne early on, and
165 deutogyne later in the season (Manson & Oldfield, 1996). In some cases, these forms
166 are so different that they have been mistakenly classified as separate species (Duso &
167 De Lillo, 1996). Reliance on morphological characteristics for identifying eriophyoids has
168 led to many taxonomic errors, underscoring the need for alternative tools to resolve
169 these challenges.

170 Eriophyoidea exhibits remarkable diversity, with over 5,000 species described
171 across three families: Phytoseiidae, Eriophyidae, and Diptilomiopidae (Amrine et al.,
172 2003; Amrine & de Lillo, unpublished database). However, this number likely represents
173 only 1-2% of the total expected species richness for this group (Ozman-Sullivan &
174 Sullivan, 2023, 2024). This gap in knowledge highlights the challenges of documenting
175 Eriophyoidea diversity, which is further compounded by a slowdown in the rate of
176 species identification and characterization, as depicted in Figure 1. Contributing factors
177 include the limited number of specialists, reduced funding for taxonomic research, and

178 under-sampling. Species description is also inherently time-consuming and requires
179 specialized expertise in acarology (de Lillo et al., 2010). All these obstacles, imposed by
180 morphology-based classification, emphasize the need for more efficient and accessible
181 diagnostic tools to accurately catalog Eriophyoidea diversity. While traditional
182 morphological identification remains a cornerstone in eriophyoid taxonomy, molecular
183 tools are becoming increasingly accessible and valuable for complementing species
184 characterization (Druciarek et al., 2019).

185 Advancements in molecular methods are transforming the way arthropods,
186 including eriophyoid mites, are identified by overcoming the limitations of morphology-
187 based classification. DNA barcoding has emerged as a crucial tool for accurate species
188 identification. Through Sanger sequencing of PCR-amplified sequences and various
189 phylogenetic methods, acarologists can reliably distinguish between cryptic species
190 (Laska et al., 2018; Skoracka & Dabert, 2010; Szydło et al., 2015; Yin et al., 2022) and
191 identify seasonal morphs in species with complex life cycles (Guo et al., 2015; Yin et al.,
192 2020). These approaches have significantly improved taxonomic precision and
193 facilitated a deeper understanding of Eriophyoidea diversity.

194 Beyond barcoding, phylogenomics has played a crucial role in revealing the
195 evolutionary relationships among eriophyoids at all taxonomic levels (Chetverikov et al.,
196 2020; Dabert et al., 2010; Druciarek et al., 2021; Klimov et al., 2018; Lewandowski et
197 al., 2014; Szudarek-Trepto et al., 2022) and shed light on factors that influence vector
198 competency, host associations, and virus-vector co-evolution. For example,
199 phylogenomic studies of *Phyllocoptes* species associated with rose rosette emaravirus
200 (RRV) transmission have clarified species boundaries, which are crucial for identifying
201 the vectors involved (Druciarek et al., 2021, 2023). Recently, HTS was used to
202 sequence and analyze the mitochondrial genomes of over 150 eriophyoid species
203 (Zhang et al., 2024). This research provided compelling evidence supporting the
204 monophyly of Eriophyoidea, while also indicating the existence of six major clades, as
205 opposed to the three currently recognized families. Despite these advancements,
206 however, the integration of molecular data into taxonomic descriptions remains limited.

207 Only 8% of eriophyoid species described between 2018 and 2022 included barcoding
208 data, reflecting a significant gap between molecular and morphological approaches.

209 This disconnect is further complicated by the scarcity of genetic markers in public
210 databases. Of the 2.3 million nucleotide sequences available in the NCBI database for
211 Acari (mites and ticks), only 0.4% are related to eriophyoid mites, despite their status
212 as one of the most species-rich group within Acari (Ozman-Sullivan & Sullivan, 2024).
213 Whole-genome sequencing for eriophyoids is still in its early stages, with only two
214 species, the tomato russet mite (TRM, *Aculops lycopersici*) and a strawberry gall-
215 inducing mite, *Fragariocoptes setiger*, having their entire genomes publicly available
216 (Greenhalgh et al., 2020; Klimov et al., 2022). The eriophyoid genetic data desert can
217 largely be attributed to their size, which complicates nucleic acid extraction and hinders
218 the development of high-throughput methodologies. These technical challenges,
219 combined with the group's cryptic nature and taxonomic complexity, have stalled
220 significant progress in molecular investigations. Much more is known about the biology
221 of larger virus vectors, such as insects and ticks, where extensive research into
222 transcriptomics, microbiomes, and host-pathogen interactions has provided a wealth of
223 insights (e.g., Martins et al., 2021; Rotenberg et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2022).

224

225 **Virus-mite-host interactions**

226 Eriophyoids are highly specialized obligate plant parasites with unique adaptations that
227 make them efficient vectors of plant viruses. Their size allows them to inhabit confined
228 spaces such as buds, leaf sheaths, and other sheltered areas (Stenger et al., 2016).

229 Many eriophyoid species induce abnormal structures on their host plants, including
230 galls, leaf curls, and erineae, which serve as both protective refuges and foraging sites.

231 These structures typically develop on young and tender tissues in response to the mites'
232 salivary secretions, which alter plant hormone balances and trigger local metabolic and
233 developmental changes in the affected cells (de Lillo et al., 2018; Paponova et al.,
234 2018). Feeding is facilitated by specialized, needle-like mouthparts derived from the
235 chelicerae, pedipalps, and labrum (de Lillo et al., 2001). These structures, which include

236 both fixed and movable digits, are not long enough (especially in phytoptids and
237 eriophyids) to penetrate beyond the thickness of a typical plant epidermal cell. They are
238 used to penetrate the cell wall just enough to access the cytoplasm (Petanović &
239 Kielkiewicz, 2010; Westphal & Manson, 1996), where viral particles can be introduced
240 to initiate infection. The complex interplay among emaraviruses, their eriophyoid mite
241 vectors, and host plants is depicted in Figure 2, illustrating the virus-vector-host
242 interactions, mite life cycle, and the environmental factors influencing disease
243 dynamics.

244 Eriophyoid mites also exhibit extreme host specificity, with 80% reported on a
245 single plant species, and 95% restricted to a single genus (Skoracka et al., 2010).
246 Similarly, a significant percentage of emaraviruses appears to be restricted to a single
247 plant genus (Table 1), reflecting the intimate evolutionary relationships among virus,
248 vector, and host. For instance, eriophyoid-induced habitats, such as galls or erineae,
249 enable mites to persist on the same host throughout their lifecycle (de Lillo et al.,
250 2018). Most species rarely cause host death by feeding alone (Sabelis & Bruin, 1996),
251 instead dispersing when the host becomes unsuitable due to environmental factors or
252 biotic pressures, such as virus-induced disease. Although emaravirus-mite-host
253 pathosystems appear fine-tuned, suggesting a steady state and uniform attributes
254 among them, contradictory data arise depending on the pathosystem studied,
255 prompting a reevaluation of many questions and hypotheses. One of the lingering
256 questions is the virus mode of transmission. Given the similarity between emaraviruses
257 and orthotospoviruses, the leading hypothesis is that emaraviruses are transmitted in a
258 persistent, propagative manner, meaning that they can enter and replicate in both plant
259 and vector cells (Chen et al., 2019; Mielke-Ehret et al., 2010; Rotenberg & Whitfield,
260 2018). There are only a few examples where this hypothesis has been tested to some
261 extent, and the results are inconsistent. Based on early studies of the transmission of
262 pigeon pea sterility mosaic emaravirus-1 (PPSMV-1), it was predicted that emaraviruses
263 are transmitted in a semi-persistent manner, as there was no detectable latent period
264 (the time between particle ingestion and virus transmission) nor evidence of

265 transovarial transmission (Kulkarni et al., 2002). The acquisition access period (AAP),
266 the time needed for the vector to acquire the virus from the host, and the inoculation
267 access period (IAP), the time needed for successful transmission to a new host, for
268 *Aceria cajani*, the vector of PPSMV-1, were 10 and 60 minutes, respectively. Pre-
269 acquisition starvation of *A. cajani* for four hours shortened AAP and IAP to 5 and 30
270 minutes, respectively (Latha & Doraiswamy, 2004). In other words, if transmission
271 mode is persistent, the virus would need roughly half an hour to cross the intestinal
272 track barrier, reach the salivary glands, and transmit to a new plant. Similarly, Perilla
273 mosaic emaravirus was transmitted at a rate of 11% after an AAP for 30 min using five
274 adult mites (Kubota, personal communication). Conversely, the latency (the time
275 between virus acquisition and transmission by a vector) for Fig mosaic emaravirus
276 (FMV) and its vector *Aceria ficus*, was determined to be 6-7 hours, suggesting semi-
277 persistent or persistent mode for FMV (Martelli et al., 2013). RRV required a much
278 longer latency of at least five days in its vector, *Phyllocoptes fructiphilus*, to be
279 successfully transmitted, suggesting a persistent, propagative mode (Di Bello, 2015; Di
280 Bello et al., 2018). Supporting this, our research on RRV indicates that viral titers within
281 the vector increase five day after acquisition, further corroborating a propagative
282 mechanism (Druciarek et al., 2024b).

283 The observed variations in transmission underscore the complexity of
284 emaravirus-vector interactions. It is increasingly evident that the transmission dynamics
285 may differ depending on the specific virus-vector pairing, potentially reflecting
286 adaptations to ecological and evolutionary pressures. For instance, differences in vector
287 competence among cryptic species or populations of eriophyoid mites may contribute to
288 inconsistencies, as not all vector populations acquire and transmit the virus equally
289 (Wosula et al., 2016). Resolving these contradictions is essential for understanding the
290 full scope of emaravirus pathosystems and their impact on plant health.

291 Advanced microscopy techniques have been pivotal in investigating the
292 localization of viruses within vector tissues, shedding light on viral movement. These
293 approaches have been applied extensively to viruses such as orthotospoviruses (Chen

294 et al., 2022a; Montero-Astúa et al., 2016) and other plant RNA viruses (Brault et al.,
295 2007; Watanabe et al., 2016) but only in a single emaravirus study (Mielke-Ehret et al.,
296 2010). Using immunofluorescence, confocal laser scanning microscopy and RT-PCR,
297 EMARaV nucleocapsid protein (P3) and viral RNA were detected within *Eriophyes pyri*, a
298 mite suspected of transmitting EMARaV. Viral proteins were not limited to the
299 mouthparts or gastrointestinal tract, but were localized in the gnathosoma and anterior
300 part of opisthosoma where salivary glands are located or within an entire body. The
301 preparation of microscopic mites for such investigations is challenging. The process
302 involves careful fixation, dehydration, and staining while minimizing damage to preserve
303 delicate tissues for imaging. These technical hurdles complicate the interpretation of
304 results, as the small scale makes distinguishing between external and internal
305 localization of viral components challenging. In this study, the detection of P3 in regions
306 associated with the salivary glands supports a propagative mode of transmission,
307 though no evidence of transovarial transmission was found as no accumulation of viral
308 proteins was observed in the oocytes or eggs (Mielke-Ehret et al., 2010). These
309 findings, while groundbreaking at the time, underscore the need for continued
310 methodological advancements and investigation of other pathosystems, including non-
311 competent species for comparison of protein accumulation in tissues, to further
312 elucidate virus-vector interactions.

313 Another notion of interest is the persistence of emaraviruses in plants. Evidence
314 suggests that many emaraviruses, including RRV, Raspberry leaf blotch emaravirus
315 (RLBV) and Blackberry leaf mottle emaravirus (BLMV) are systemic, as they were
316 detected in the roots of their hosts, where vectors are absent (Delić et al., 2020; Di
317 Bello et al., 2018; Druciarek et al., 2024a). However, in some pathosystems, such as
318 that of RLBV and *Phyllocoptes gracilis*, eliminating the mite vector can lead to symptom
319 remission with the virus becoming undetectable (T. Druciarek, unpublished data).
320 Similar observations were previously reported for *P. gracilis* - initially thought by itself to
321 be the cause of blotching symptoms on tayberries, where the application of miticide
322 significantly reduced mite populations and led to a marked decrease in symptom

323 severity over consecutive growing seasons (Jones et al., 1984). This is not
324 unprecedented as the same has been observed in other virus-arthropod pathosystems
325 (Larrea-Sarmiento et al., 2021), suggesting that the continuous presence of a vector
326 could be critical for symptom expression. Another explanation is the uneven distribution
327 of emaraviruses in their woody hosts, as also observed with other viruses infecting such
328 hosts (Villamor et al., 2022). In the case of RRV, the virus was detected in 50% of
329 infected plant roots (Di Bello et al., 2018), and for BLMV, the virus was present in only
330 15% of the plants that gave strong positives the previous season (A. Sierra-Mejia and I.
331 Tzanetakis, unpublished data). A similar situation has been observed with field grown
332 blackberries, where BLMV caused close to 100% infection in one season, and was
333 virtually absent the next (T. Ho, personal communication).

334 The conflicting data on symptom persistence following mite removal highlights a
335 potential dependence of emaravirus pathosystems on vector presence, underscoring a
336 significant research gap in understanding these dynamics. RNA silencing suppression
337 activity has been identified for gene products of several emaraviruses, with the
338 exemplar High Plains wheat mosaic emaravirus (HPWMOV) encoding two silencing
339 suppressing proteins with distinct activities (Gupta et al., 2019). Yet the hosts are able
340 to counter given that initial infection often causes severe symptoms that subsequently
341 diminish, with plants appearing healthy later in the same or following seasons
342 (Chellappan et al., 2004; Garcia-Ruiz, 2019; Ghoshal & Sanfaçon, 2015; Wingard,
343 1928). The interactions between virus, vector, and host require substantial investigation
344 to unravel the mechanisms driving their diverse functions.

345

346 **Epidemiology**

347 The epidemiology of emaravirus-caused diseases is still an emerging field, with more
348 questions than answers. This knowledge gap significantly hampers efforts to control
349 emaravirus diseases, as effective management strategies are rooted in a thorough
350 understanding of epidemiological dynamics. As noted, a significant percentage of
351 emaraviruses is restricted to a single host genus, possibly due to the host specificity of

352 their vectors. This limiting factor confines emaraviruses only to areas where vector and
353 the host are present, minimizing the risk of virus spread over large distances or into
354 new agricultural regions, unless viruliferous mites or infected host plants are
355 introduced.

356 However, while the narrow host range reduces the likelihood of a large-scale
357 epidemic, the close interactions between virus, vector, and host may lead to intense
358 outbreaks. If vector populations remain unchecked, or if there is a substantial increase
359 in host density – such as in monoculture agriculture – viruses can spread rapidly
360 (Regassa, 2022; Whitfield et al., 2015). These outbreaks may have devastating
361 consequences, such as for the rose industry due to rose rosette disease (RRD) or
362 severe food insecurity for communities relying on pigeonpea as a primary protein
363 source during pigeonpea sterility mosaic disease (PSMD) epidemics (Babu et al., 2018;
364 Jones et al., 2004).

365 Environmental factors such as temperature and humidity play a critical role in
366 shaping the population dynamics of eriophyoid mites and, consequently, virus
367 transmission (Karpicka-Ignatowska et al., 2021; Kuczyński et al., 2016; Monterrosa et
368 al., 2022). An example of how the combination of favorable climatic conditions
369 alongside cultural practices can cause epidemics is the case of PSMD, caused by
370 PPSMV-1 and pigeonpea sterility mosaic emaravirus 2 (PPSMV-2). PSMD is the most
371 devastating virus disease affecting pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan*) (Elbeaino et al., 2014;
372 Kumar et al., 2017). Infection by the two viruses often results in total loss if infection
373 occurs early in the season (Jones et al., 2004). Sayiprathap et al. (2020) highlighted the
374 role of environmental factors, such as temperature and humidity, which likely influenced
375 both, the mite vector population, and the transmission dynamics of viruses. Specifically,
376 regions with monocultures of susceptible pigeonpea varieties showed higher incidences
377 of PSMD with losses reaching as high as 97% (Kannaiyan et al., 1984).

378 Additionally, human activity plays a significant role in spreading viruses and their
379 vectors through the movement of infected plant material, leading to the establishment
380 of diseases in previously unaffected regions (Miedaner & Garbelotto, 2024; Ranawaka

381 et al., 2020). As an example, RRV, the causal agent of RRD, has led to a devastating
382 epidemic throughout the United States (Pemberton et al., 2018). The prevalence of
383 RRD has reached such alarming levels that roses are not recommended for planting in
384 certain areas (Holloway, 2015). Both virus and vectoring mites are considered native to
385 North America, having coevolved with indigenous rose species in the Rocky Mountains,
386 which have developed partial tolerance to RRD (Amrine, 2014). A trigger to the rose
387 rosette outbreak was the introduction and widespread planting of multiflora rose (*Rosa*
388 *multiflora*). Because of its prolific seed production and spread by birds, it became
389 considered a noxious weed in multiple states and RRV was proposed as a biological
390 control with infected material used informally for that purpose. Eventually multiflora
391 rose became an excellent host for both, vectoring mites and the virus, providing a new
392 avenue for disease proliferation across the continent (Byrne et al., 2018).

393 The narrow host and vector specificity of emaraviruses can act as an effective
394 containment factor. It limits the virus' spread across diverse ecosystems and specificity
395 also provides with potential avenues for control. Quarantine is an effective measure to
396 prevent the introduction of emaraviruses and their vectors to new territory. For
397 example, even though RRV is prevalent in the United States there is a single
398 interception outside North America (Chakraborty et al., 2017). The same is true for
399 RLBV and BLMV which appear to be confined to Europe and North America,
400 respectively. Despite significant movement of planting material between continents,
401 neither virus has been detected beyond its natural geographic range. However,
402 exceptions to this pattern highlight the potential risks posed by a generalist vector.
403 HPWMoV is a virus with a global distribution, present on multiple continents (Tatineni &
404 Hein, 2021). This widespread occurrence is linked to its vector, the wheat curl mite
405 (WCM, *Aceria tosichella*). Unlike many eriophyoid species, WCM is a generalist with an
406 extraordinary capacity for dispersal and adaptation, facilitated by its ability to infest a
407 broad range of grass hosts (Navia et al., 2013; Skoracka et al., 2018a).

408

409 **Control**

410 While mites move slowly between plants in the field, aerial dispersal by wind currents
411 allows them to travel efficiently to neighboring plants and even over long distances,
412 including through the upper atmosphere (Duffner et al., 2001; Laska et al., 2023; Majer
413 et al., 2021; Zhao & Amrine, 1997). The ecological adaptations of specific vectors and
414 the cropping systems of their hosts significantly influence the spread of these mites and
415 the viruses they carry. For instance, dense monoculture plantings, such as in cereals,
416 facilitate mite dispersal between plants, accelerating the rate of infection (Krupinsky et
417 al., 2002; Skoracka et al., 2018b).

418 Controlling the WCM, the vector of HPWMoV, through pesticide application is
419 often ineffective due to the mites' secluded habitat within the whorls of wheat plants.
420 However cultural practices can be used to manage HPWMoV and other WCM-
421 transmitted viruses. One such practice involves breaking the disease cycle by destroying
422 volunteer wheat (the green bridge) at least two weeks before planting. This interrupts
423 the mite's lifecycle, reduces virus reservoirs, and mitigates early infestations and
424 transmission risks (Tatineni & Hein, 2021; Wegulo et al., 2008).

425 By targeting the vector or interrupting interaction mechanisms in a fine-tuned tri-
426 trophic system, the spread of emaraviruses could be contained more effectively, than in
427 systems where the vector or host range is broader and interaction mechanisms less
428 specific. The adaptation and the dependency of the mite to their host is challenging to
429 alter, as any significant change would greatly impact the mite's survival, making
430 resistance difficult to overcome (Akam, 2000; de Lillo et al., 2018; Skoracka et al.,
431 2010). Notwithstanding research has shown that resistance to specialized mites is not
432 common (Gill et al., 2024). It is therefore not surprising that the most promising
433 research when it comes to mite resistance addresses a generalist, the WCM (Nachappa
434 et al., 2021). Research spanning several decades has identified several sources of
435 resistance (Dhakal et al., 2017; Harvey et al., 1999; Malik et al., 2003; Zhao et al.,
436 2021), which have been deployed to control vector and viruses (Chuang et al., 2017;
437 Rudd et al., 2014). However, widespread use of one WCM resistance gene has been
438 shown to lead to the development of mite lineages that overcame resistance (Harvey et

439 al., 1999). Pigeonpea sterility has been studied in depth because of its significance and
440 there are several wild genotypes identified that did not support *A. cajani* populations
441 (Kumar et al., 2005). Recent work by Murtujasab et al. (2024) has yielded promising
442 results regarding the disease and identified anatomical features in resistant accessions
443 that could influence mite feeding. However, these findings did not include the study of
444 mite populations on the plants. Information on resistance to other emaravirus vectors
445 remains limited. In the case of rose rosette, Di Bello et al. (2018) failed to identify any
446 genotypes able to suppress mite colonization of *P. fructiphilus*, whereas Solo et al.
447 (2019) reported differences in mite population numbers across various genotypes, but
448 these findings lacked consistency between seasons. Recent studies have identified
449 quantitative trait loci (QTLs) associated with resistance to RRD in both diploid and
450 tetraploid roses (Hochhaus et al., 2023; Lau et al., 2022; Young et al., 2022). These
451 findings highlight genetic regions linked to partial resistance, including mechanisms
452 related to antiviral defense and virus replication. However, whether these genetic
453 factors also influence resistance to mite vectors remains unknown. It is evident that,
454 apart from the WCM, research on resistance against emaravirus vectors is still in its
455 infancy. Further exploration in this area could yield valuable tools for disease control.

456 As we further investigate eriophyoid mites more control possibilities arise. For
457 example, acaricides can diminish mite populations and minimize transmission,
458 especially, in cases like RRV where there is a significant AAP during which the active
459 ingredients can target mites during feeding and viral acquisition. However, challenges
460 remain in ensuring effective coverage, as mites often inhabit concealed microhabitats
461 such as induced abnormalities, leaf sheaths and buds (Van Leeuwen et al., 2010;
462 Vervaeet et al., 2021). Of course, mites are no exception, and continuous use of
463 chemical pesticides also leads to the development of resistance in mite pest populations
464 (Arthur et al., 2021; Van Leeuwen et al., 2010; Xu et al., 2018). Increasing awareness
465 of the risks associated with systemic pesticides has led to stricter regulations and the
466 withdrawal of certain active ingredients from the market. For example, the European
467 Union has implemented bans on specific neonicotinoids and other active ingredients

468 used in plant protection products due to their harmful effects on pollinators, the
469 environment, and human health (Butler-Dawson et al., 2018; Jactel et al., 2019). As a
470 consequence, in some countries, such as Poland, there are no longer any acaricides
471 registered for use against the mites in raspberry, a host of a devastating emaravirus
472 disease.

473 Biological control offers a sustainable alternative for managing eriophyoid vector
474 populations. Entomopathogenic or acaropathogenic species belonging to at least ten
475 different genera have been evaluated in the past against eriophyoid mites, with the
476 most effective reported in the genus *Beauveria*, *Hirsutella*, *Metarhizium*, and *Meira* (El-
477 Sharabasy, 2015; Gerson et al., 2009; McCoy, 1996; Minguely et al., 2021; Paz et al.,
478 2007). For instance, *B. bassiana* induced up to 80% mortality in *P. gracilis*,
479 demonstrating its potential as biocontrol agent. Preliminary evidence (T. Druciarek, and
480 I. Tzanetakis, unpublished data) suggests that certain acaropathogenic yeasts and
481 higher ascomycetes can eliminate *P. fructiphilus* colonies in a short period of time. A
482 key advantage of acaropathogens lies in their ability to exploit the microclimatic
483 conditions in which eriophyoid mites thrive. Mites often inhabit dark, moist
484 microhabitats such as buds, leaf sheaths, and petiole bases, where high humidity
485 provides optimal conditions for fungal growth and spore dissemination. Upon contact
486 with fungal spores and hyphae, mites become infected, and eventually the fungi cause
487 death. Once the host is depleted, fungal hyphae grow out of the mite cadaver,
488 producing secondary spores that act as inoculum for other mites (McCoy, 1996).
489 Windborne character of mites' dispersal could further aid in the dissemination of fungal
490 spores to untreated areas, potentially amplifying their impact.

491 Predatory mites have demonstrated potential for controlling eriophyoid mites,
492 with some species consuming over 100 individuals per day (Vervaet et al., 2021), in the
493 case of *P. fructiphilus* (vector of RRV), over 150 individuals daily—an excellent rate by
494 any measure (T. Druciarek and I. Tzanetakis, unpublished). While these findings are
495 promising, most studies on predatory mites focus on larger prey, like spider mites or
496 thrips, leaving significant gaps in our understanding of eriophyoids as prey or as

497 alternative food sources for these predators (Sabelis & Van Rijn, 1996). The concealed
498 microhabitats of eriophyoids, such as galls and leaf sheaths, may also limit the
499 effectiveness of predation. Nevertheless, if properly selected, predatory mites,
500 particularly in combination with other control measures, offers a promising avenue for
501 reducing eriophyoid populations and virus transmission in some of the emaravirus-
502 related pathosystems.

503

504 **Challenges in the emaravirus/vector arena:**

505 There has been significant progress in understanding emaravirus/vector pathosystems
506 but there is ample space for improvement. The major bottleneck is the scarcity of
507 research groups specializing in eriophyoids and mite-borne diseases, primarily because
508 of the lack of expertise and resources needed. This is the primary reason for the lack of
509 confirmed vectors among many emaraviruses (Table 1), despite advancements in
510 molecular tools that facilitate accurate mite barcoding, and assist in selecting potential
511 vectors by enabling the quantifiable detection of viruses within mite bodies (Druciarek
512 et al., 2024b; Hassan et al., 2017; Luigi et al., 2024; Olmedo-Velarde et al., 2019,
513 2021).

514 Indeed, transmission studies pose a major obstacle without the expertise of an
515 acarologist. Establishing pure mite colonies is difficult, because, as noted, they have
516 specific environmental and host plant requirements that are difficult to replicate in
517 laboratory settings (Oldfield & Perring, 1996); especially for refugee-seeking species. It
518 is also important to precisely execute those experiments. While there have been various
519 methods employed to establish populations in culture (McGavin et al., 2012; Nene &
520 Reddy, 1976; Rosarid & Sill, 1958), single mite or egg transfer is desired (de Lillo et al.,
521 2021; Skare et al., 2003). This approach minimizes the risk of accidentally transferring
522 multiple species from co-infested plants and ensures a pure colony, critical for
523 maintaining the integrity of the study. In addition, it allows researchers to identify the
524 mite life stage and transfer a known number of mites for estimating transmission
525 efficiencies.

526 Given the inconsistencies of the studies that investigated the transmission mode
527 of emaraviruses, this aspect of epidemiology should be the next challenge to tackle. It
528 remains unclear why certain *Phyllocoptes* mites, such as *P. fructiphilus* and *P. arcani*,
529 can transmit a virus, whereas closely related species, like *P. adalius*, cannot (Di Bello et
530 al., 2018; Druciarek et al., 2023; Druciarek, et al., 2024b). There is a lack of data
531 explaining what makes a mite species an effective emaravirus vector. Factors that may
532 influence vector competency, as seen in other vector groups, could include receptor-
533 mediated virus binding, anatomical or physiological barriers, immune responses,
534 microbial symbionts, feeding behavior, or co-evolutionary adaptations with the virus
535 (Bragard et al., 2013; Olagunju, 2024; Whitfield et al., 2015). Understanding these
536 mechanisms for emaraviruses and eriophyoid mites remains a critical knowledge gap
537 that warrants further investigation. It is important to dissect the molecular mechanisms
538 underlying acquisition and transmission, as they can provide vital clues for developing
539 targeted strategies to mitigate disease impact. Furthermore, the variability in vector
540 competence amongst mite populations or cryptic species can affect transmission
541 dynamics and complicate epidemiological predictions. For example, *Phyllocoptes arcani*,
542 a vector of RRV, had previously been observed (J. Amrine, personal communication) yet
543 it was dismissed as a distinct population of *P. fructiphilus*. Similarly, the case of
544 *Phyllocoptes parviflori*, the vector of BLMV, underscores the importance of accurate
545 taxonomic and vector competence assessments. Described over 80 years ago, *P.*
546 *parviflori* was synonymized with *P. gracilis* due to morphological similarities, but was
547 recently reinstated as a distinct species (Druciarek et al., 2024a; Keifer, 1952). The
548 geographic confinement of BLMV and its vector to North America, and RLBV and its
549 putative vector *P. gracilis* to Europe, underscores the role of host and vector specificity
550 in limiting their spread. These findings emphasize the need for a deeper understanding
551 of vector diversity and competence, as such nuances directly influence the epidemiology
552 and management of emaravirus-related diseases.

553 There is a clear need to better understand the plant responses to both viruses
554 and vectors. How can it be that a virus is systemic and yet it becomes undetectable? Is

555 it lost or will it reemerge once the conditions are favorable? Answers to those questions
556 are essential to better address diseases and the appropriate control approaches.
557 Understanding plant responses to mites are also important as we can identify pathways
558 or compounds that can be used in the breeding process to develop resistant cultivars as
559 done for other vectors (Smith, 2021; Srinivasan et al., 2018; Talakayala et al., 2020).

560

561 **Conclusions and future perspectives**

562 Despite significant progress in understanding emaravirus-host-vector interactions, many
563 knowledge gaps remain. It is likely that a substantial proportion of emaravirus-caused
564 diseases result in asymptomatic infections, which remain undetected in current
565 research. With only 35 recognized or putative emaraviruses identified to date, our
566 understanding likely represents just a fraction of their true diversity. Plant virome
567 studies are heavily biased toward symptomatic samples and economically significant
568 plants, leaving infections in less conspicuous hosts largely unexplored. HTS, while
569 transformative, remains costly and labor-intensive, further limiting the exploration of
570 plant viromes in diverse ecosystems. Given the vast diversity of plant species
571 (estimated at around 400,000) it is conceivable that there are hundreds of thousands of
572 eriophyoid species yet to be discovered, many of which are associated with plants of
573 low economic significance. These likely asymptomatic mite-host associations are rarely
574 studied, potentially concealing a wide array of undiscovered emaraviruses.

575 Understanding the intricate interactions among virus, vector, and host is
576 essential for developing targeted and effective management strategies for emaravirus
577 diseases. Traditional morphology-based taxonomy has become increasingly insufficient
578 given the complexity of the group's evolutionary history and the prevalence of cryptic
579 species. Molecular methods, such as DNA barcoding and phylogenomic, have proven
580 invaluable in addressing these gaps and enhancing our understanding of eriophyoid
581 diversity and evolutionary relationships. However, the limited integration of molecular
582 data into species descriptions, alongside the technical challenges, continues to slow
583 progress. Further advancements in molecular techniques will be critical in identifying

584 vector species and unraveling the complex dynamics between eriophyoid mites and the
585 viruses they transmit. As more genomic resources become available and research
586 capacity expands, particularly in the study of mite-borne diseases, the potential to
587 unlock new insights into these ecologically and economically significant arthropods will
588 undoubtedly grow.

589 The epidemiology of emaraviruses is deeply intertwined with the biology and
590 behavior of their eriophyoid vectors, as well as environmental and human factors.
591 Continued research into vector competence, ecological adaptations, and environmental
592 influences, will be essential for developing long-term management solutions. Integrated
593 pest management approaches, including the use of biocontrol agents, quarantine
594 measures, and mite-resistant cultivars, offer promising strategies for mitigating the
595 impact of emaraviruses. As -omics tools are adapted for use on individual eriophyoids,
596 they will unlock transformative insights into these highly specialized arthropods and the
597 viruses they vector, enabling more sustainable and innovative solutions for managing
598 emaravirus-associated diseases.

599

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615 During the preparation of this work the authors used GhatGPT v.4 in order to improve
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618

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621 **References**

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Table 1. List of emaraviruses transmitted by eriophyoid mites.

	Virus name (acronym)	Virus species with ICTV taxon link	Plant host(s) reported	Reported from	Vector species	Key reference(s)
1	actinidia chlorotic ringspot-associated emaravirus (AcCRaV)	Emaravirus actinidiae	<i>Actinidia</i> sp.	China	Unknown	(Zheng et al., 2017)
2	actinidia emaravirus 2 (AcV-2)	Emaravirus kiwii	<i>Actinidia eriantha</i> , <i>A. chinensis</i> , <i>A. deliciosa</i>	China	Unknown	(Wang et al., 2020a)
3	ailanthus crinkle leaf-associated virus (ACrLaV)	Emaravirus ailanthi	Tree of heaven (<i>Ailanthus altissima</i>)	China	Unknown	(An et al., 2022)
4	arceuthobium sichuanense-associated virus 1 (ArSaV-1)	Emaravirus visci	Spruce dwarf mistletoe (<i>Arceuthobium sichuanense</i>)	China	Unknown	(Sidharthan et al., 2022)
5	artemisia fimovirus 1 (ArtV1)	Emaravirus artemisiae	<i>Artemisia verlotiorum</i>	Slovenia	Unknown	(Rivarez et al., 2023)
6	ash shoestring-associated virus (ASaV)	Emaravirus fraxini	European ash (<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>) and manna ash (<i>F. ornus</i>)	Germany, Switzerland, Sweden, Italy	Unknown	(Gaskin et al., 2021)
7	aspen mosaic-associated virus (AsMaV)	Emaravirus populi	Eurasian aspen (<i>Populus tremula</i>)	Norway, Finland and Sweden	Unknown	(von Bargaen et al., 2020)
8	blackberry leaf mottle emaravirus (BLMV)	Emaravirus rubi	Blackberry (<i>Rubus</i> subg. <i>Rubus</i> Watson), black raspberry (<i>Rubus occidentalis</i>)	USA	<i>Phyllocoptes parviflori</i>	(Druciarek et al., 2024a; Hassan et al., 2017)
9	camellia japonica-associated virus 1 (CjaV-1)	Emaravirus camelliae	Common camellia (<i>Camellia japonica</i>)	Italy, China	Unknown	(Peracchio et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020)
10	camellia japonica-associated virus 2	Emaravirus	Common	Italy, China	Unknown	(Peracchio et

	(CjaV-2)	verbanni	camellia (<i>Camellia japonica</i>)			al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020)
11	chrysanthemum mosaic-associated emaravirus (ChMaV)	Emaravirus chrysanthemi	Chrysanthemum (cv. 'Kinnishiki')	Japan	<i>Paraphytoptus kikus</i> (suspected, not confirmed)	(Kubota et al., 2021b)
12	common oak ringspot-associated virus (CORaV)	Emaravirus quercus	Common oak (<i>Quercus robur</i>)	Germany, Sweden, Norway	Unknown	(Bandte et al., 2020; Rehanek et al., 2021)
13	European mountain ash ringspot-associated emaravirus (EMARaV)	Emaravirus sorbi	European mountain ash, rowan (<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>) and Swedish whitebeam (<i>S. intermedia</i>), serviceberry (<i>Amelanchier</i> spp.) and other Rosaceae species	North and Central Europe	<i>Eriophyes pyri</i> (suspected, not confirmed)	(Grimová et al., 2015; Mielke & Muehlbach, 2007; von Bargen et al., 2019)
14	fig mosaic emaravirus (FMV)	Emaravirus fici	Fig (<i>Ficus carica</i> , <i>F. pseudocarica</i>), cyclamen (<i>Cyclamen persicum</i>)	North America, Europe, North Africa, Middle East, Asia, New Zealand	<i>Aceria ficus</i>	(Elbeaino et al., 2009a, 2009b; Ishikawa et al., 2012; Martelli et al., 2013)
15	High Plains wheat mosaic emaravirus (HPWMoV)	Emaravirus tritici	wheat, maize, barley, oat, rye, cheat, green and yellow foxtail	Central and Western USA, Canada, Argentina, Australia, Ukraine	<i>Aceria tosichella</i>	(Jensen et al., 1996; Tatineni et al., 2014; Tatineni & Hein, 2021)
16	Japanese star anise ringspot-associated virus (JSaRaV)	Emaravirus illicii	Japanese star anise (<i>Illicium anisatum</i>)	Japan	species of the family Diptilomiopidae	(Shimomoto et al., 2022)
17	jujube yellow mottle-associated emaravirus (JYMaV)	Emaravirus ziziphi	Jujube, Chinese date (<i>Ziziphus</i>)	China	Unknown	(Liu et al., 2020a; Yang

			<i>jujube</i>)			et al., 2019)
18	Karaka Okahu purepure emaravirus (KOPV)	Emaravirus corynocarpi	Karaka (<i>Corynocarpus laevigatus</i>)	New Zealand	<i>Aculus corynocarpi</i> (suspected, not confirmed)	(Rabbidge, 2021; Rabbidge et al., 2021)
19	lilac chlorotic ringspot-associated emaravirus (LiCRaV)	Emaravirus syringae	Common lilac (<i>Syringa vulgaris</i>)	China	Unknown	(Wang et al., 2020b)
20	maple mottle-associated emaravirus (MaMaV)	Emaravirus aceris	Maple (<i>Acer</i> spp.)	Germany	Unknown	(Rumbou et al., 2021)
21	palo verde broom virus (PVBV)	Emaravirus parkinsoniae	Blue palo verde tree (<i>Parkinsonia florida</i>)	USA, Mexico	Unknown	(Ilyas et al., 2018)
22	pear chlorotic leaf spot-associated emaravirus (PCLSaV)	Emaravirus pyri	Asian pear (<i>Pyrus pyrifolia</i>),	China, Japan	<i>Eriophyes chibaensis</i>	(Kubota et al., 2020b; Liu et al., 2020b)
23	perilla mosaic emaravirus (PerMV)	Emaravirus perillae	Beefsteak plant, Shiso (<i>Perilla frutescens</i>)	Japan, South Korea	<i>Shevtchenkella</i> sp.	(Chiaki & Kubota, 2024; Kubota et al., 2020a)
24	pigeonpea sterility mosaic emaravirus 1 (PPSMV-1)	Emaravirus cajani	Pigeonpea (<i>Cajanus cajan</i>)	South Asia	<i>Aceria cajani</i>	(Elbeaino et al., 2014; Kumar et al., 2000, 2003, 2017)
25	pigeonpea sterility mosaic emaravirus 2 (PPSMV-2)	Emaravirus toordali	Pigeonpea (<i>Cajanus cajan</i>)	South Asia	<i>Aceria cajani</i>	(Elbeaino et al., 2015; Patil et al., 2017)
26	pistacia emaravirus B (PIVB)	Emaravirus pistaciae	Pistachio (<i>Pistacia vera</i>) and <i>P. khinjuk</i>	Turkey	Unknown	(Buzkan et al., 2019)
27	pueraria lobata-associated emaravirus (PloAEV)	Emaravirus kudzu	Kudzu (<i>Pueraria lobata</i>)	China	Unknown	(Liang et al., 2022)
28	raspberry leaf blotch emaravirus (RLBV)	Emaravirus idaeobati	<i>Rubus</i> sp.	U.K., Serbia, Finland, Bulgaria,	<i>Phyllocoptes gracilis</i>	(Lu et al., 2015; McGavin et

				Poland, Montenegro, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kazakhstan, Ukraine		al., 2012)
29	redbud yellow ringspot-associated emaravirus (RYRaV)	Emaravirus cercidis	Redbud (<i>Cercis</i> spp.)	USA	Unknown	(Di Bello et al., 2016)
30	rose rosette emaravirus (RRV)	Emaravirus rosae	Rose (<i>Rosa</i> sp.)	USA, Canada, India	<i>Phyllocoptes fructiphilus</i> and <i>P. arcani</i>	(Di Bello et al., 2015, 2018; Druciarek et al., 2023; Laney et al., 2011)
31	ti ringspot-associated virus (TiRSaV)	Emaravirus cordylinae	Ti (<i>Cordyline fruticosa</i>)	Hawaii	Unknown	(Olmedo-Velarde et al., 2019)
32	vitis emaravirus (VEV)	Emaravirus vitis	Grape vine (<i>Vitis vinifera</i>), crimson glory vine (<i>Vitis coignetiae</i>)	Japan, China	Unknown	(Fan et al., 2021; Nabeshima & Abe, 2021)
	PUTATIVE EMARAVIRUSES:					
33	clematis yellow mottle associated virus (CYMaV)	N/A	<i>Clematis brevicaudata</i>	China	Unknown	(Yang et al., 2024)
34	pea associated emaravirus (PaEV)	N/A	Green pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>)	Germany	Unknown	(Gaafar et al., 2020)
35	woolly burdock yellow vein virus (WBYVV)	N/A	Woolly burdock (<i>Arctium tomentosum</i>)	Finland	Unknown	(Bi et al., 2012)
36	Yunnan emaralikevirus	N/A	Unknown	China	Unknown	(Chen et al., 2022b)
37	Emaravirus sp. 'urochloe'	N/A	<i>Urochloa</i> sp.?	Brazil	Unknown	N/A

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N/A – not applicable

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1365 **Figure 1.** Trends in the discovery of eriophyoid mite species over time: **(A)** The annual
1366 discovery rate of species during the 21st century (2001–2023), highlighting a significant
1367 downward trend (dashed line), with an average decrease of approx. 2.16 species
1368 described per year ($y = -2.16$). The low R^2 value (0.15) indicates considerable
1369 variability in discovery rates, likely influenced by factors such as retiring taxonomists,
1370 shifting research priorities, and funding availability. **(B)** The cumulative number of
1371 species described per decade (1920–2019), showing periods of increased taxonomic
1372 activity, particularly between 2000–2009. The decline in the 2010–2019 decade reflects
1373 a slowdown in discoveries, despite historical growth over the last century.
1374 Improved species descriptions over the past three decades have followed higher
1375 taxonomic standards, enhancing quality compared to earlier decades (E. de Lillo,
1376 personal communication). Data for these graphs were sourced from Amrine & de Lillo,
1377 (unpublished database) and supplemented with records from publicly available
1378 databases, including SCOPUS and Google Scholar, to ensure accuracy.

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Figure 2. Interactions and disease cycle of raspberry leaf blotch emaravirus (RLBV) and its eriophyid vector, *Phyllocoptes gracilis*. The diagram outlines the major stages and interactions in the disease cycle of raspberry leaf blotch disorder. **(1)** The virus multiplies and disperses with its eriophyid vector, initiating the disease cycle. **(2)** Mites transmit the virus to host plants during feeding; their life cycle includes four stages (egg, larva, nymph, and adult). **(3)** Virus infection triggers symptom development, such as blotch formation on raspberry leaves, and fosters an increase in mite populations. The diagram highlights the complex key relationships – plant-virus, virus-vector, and

1397 plant-vector – shaped by environmental conditions.

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